

The demographics of the 10 teams that participated in our qualitative evaluation; we obtained the demographic information from the teams' survey responses and the backlog size from the backlog management tool.

Team number	Team size (# members)	Years of existence	Product Owner stability (did the team have the same PO in the past year?)	Team distribution (is the team globally distributed?)	Application domain	Backlog size at the time of the interview
Team 1 (t01)	7	2 years	Yes	Yes	Cloud-based	73 stories
Team 2 (t02)	6	1 year	Yes	No	Web	44 stories
Team 3 (t03)	7	3 years	Yes	No	Web	129 stories
Team 4 (t02)	5	4 years	Yes	Yes	Mobile	87 stories
Team 5 (t03)	6	> 5 years	Yes	No	AI/Data Science	119 stories
Team 6 (t02)	4	5 years	No	No	Mobile	59 stories
Team 7 (t03)	8	3 years	Yes	No	Web	68 stories
Team 8 (t02)	5	> 5 years	Yes	No	Desktop	106 stories
Team 9 (t03)	9	4 years	No	Yes	Web	121 stories
Team 10 (t10)	5	1 year	Yes	No	AI/Data Science	37 stories